

Factors Influencing Literature Appreciation and Comprehension of Grade 5 Students in Dupax Del Sur District

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literary appreciation, reading comprehension, teaching strategies, instructional materials, Grade 5 pupils

Abstract. Literature plays a significant role in education, helping students improve their reading comprehension, critical thinking, creativity, communication skills, and cultural awareness. This study examined the factors that influence the appreciation and understanding of literature among Grade 5 students in Dupax Del Sur District, Division of Nueva Vizcaya, during the 2025–2026 school year. It focused on students' backgrounds, the motivations in teaching literature, the effectiveness of teaching methods and strategies, the instructional materials used, the level of comprehension, the development of literary appreciation, the problems faced, and the measures taken to improve. This study also explored the differences, relationships, and associations among several factors affecting literary appreciation and comprehension. A descriptive-correlational research design was used, with a researcher-made questionnaire checklist as the main tool for gathering data from thirty-five respondents chosen through purposive sampling. The data were analyzed using frequency count, percentage, weighted mean, standard deviation, ANOVA, Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient, t-test, Chi-square Test of Association, and regression analysis. The findings showed that the students had effective literary appreciation and satisfactory comprehension of the literary works. Motivational strategies, teaching methods, instructional materials, and evaluative tools were effective in boosting students' engagement and participation in literature classes. The study also found no significant differences in literary appreciation based on age or gender. However, comprehension level was significantly related to literary appreciation, and the favorite genre of literature was significantly linked to comprehension level. Regression analysis indicated that motivation in teaching literature, teaching strategies, learning materials, and comprehension level significantly influenced literary appreciation, with comprehension level being the strongest predictor. The study concluded that effective teaching practices and improved comprehension skills are crucial for enhancing students' literary appreciation.

Introduction

Literature holds a significant position in education, as it aids learners in developing reading comprehension, critical thinking, creativity, communication skills, and cultural awareness. Through literary texts such as stories, poems, and essays, learners acquire knowledge, values, and an understanding of diverse experiences and perspectives. In elementary education, literature is crucial for enhancing children's language skills and fostering positive attitudes toward reading and learning (Kuznetsova et al., 2023; Fitriyani et al., 2025). Nevertheless, numerous schools worldwide continue to encounter challenges in promoting reading habits and literary appreciation among their learners. The growing prevalence of technology and digital media has impacted students' interest in reading printed literary texts. Consequently, educators are encouraged to employ innovative teaching strategies and technology-based instructional materials to make literature lessons more engaging and meaningful for learners (Sarzhanova et al., 2025; Spjeldnæs and Karlsen, 2022). Research indicates that effective teaching strategies and interactive learning activities can enhance students' participation and appreciation of literature (Zamiri & Esmaeili, 2024).

In the Philippines, the Department of Education is making efforts to boost literacy programs to help students read and appreciate literature. One key initiative is the Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE), which uses students' native languages in the early years of schooling to make lessons more understandable (Tungul & Lapinid, 2024). However, despite these efforts, many schools still face challenges, such as a lack of teaching materials, limited access to technology, and students' lack of interest in reading. Teachers also find it difficult to use learner-centered and contextualized teaching strategies in literature classes (Jesus, 2021).

In the Dupa Del Sur District, Grade 5 students show distinct levels of interest in and appreciation for literature. Some students struggle with understanding literary texts because of limited vocabulary, lack of reading materials, and low participation in reading activities. Teachers also find it challenging to motivate students and make literature lessons engaging. These issues point to the need to assess how Grade 5 students appreciate literature and find ways to improve literature teaching in the district. While many studies have focused on reading comprehension and language learning, few have looked into how elementary students appreciate literature, especially in rural school districts. In fact, no study has yet been conducted in the Dupax Del Sur District on the literary appreciation of Grade 5 students. This gap in the research prompted the current study's investigation.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the factors influencing literature appreciation and comprehension among Grade 5 pupils in the Dupax Del Sur District, Division of Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines. Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions.

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of age, gender, reading materials available at home, favorite genre of literature, usual time spent reading literary pieces, and encountered interpreters of literature?
2. What is the extent of motivation and effectiveness of literature teaching in terms of: teaching methods, teaching strategies, learning materials and evaluative tools?
3. What is the level of comprehension and literary appreciation demonstrated by students?
4. What problems are encountered in teaching and learning literature, and what enhancement measures may be proposed to improve pupils' literary appreciation and comprehension?
5. Is there a significant difference in literary appreciation when respondents are grouped according to age and gender?
6. Are there a committed relationship and association among comprehension level, literary appreciation, and favorite genre of literature?
7. Which factors significantly affect the literary appreciation of Grade 5 pupils?

Theoretical & Conceptual Framing

The figure illustrates the theoretical and conceptual framework of the study concerning the literary appreciation of Grade 5 pupils in the Dupax Del Sur District, Division of Nueva Vizcaya. The theoretical framework is grounded in Constructivist Learning Theory, which posits that learners develop understanding through active engagement and interaction with texts, teachers, and peers. Complementary theories, including the Social Learning Theory, Reader-Response Theory, Schema Theory, and Multiple Intelligences Theory, underscore that literary appreciation is shaped by social interaction, firsthand experiences, prior knowledge, and diverse learning styles. These theories support the notion that pupils learn and appreciate literature more effectively when they are actively engaged in meaningful, learner-centered activities. The conceptual framework adheres to the input-process-output (IPO) model. The input encompassed the profile of the pupils, such as age, gender, reading materials available at home, preferred literary genre, usual reading time, and encountered interpreters of literature. The process involves the motivations, teaching strategies and methods, instructional materials, learning activities, and evaluation employed in teaching literature. Through these processes, the anticipated output is the enhancement of literary appreciation among Grade 5 students, characterized by an improved understanding of literary texts, positive attitudes toward reading, and active classroom participation. The feedback mechanism further suggests that the study's findings may be utilized to improve literature instruction and enhance learners' literary appreciation within the district.

Figure 1 Factors Influencing Literature Appreciation and Comprehension of Students

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive-correlational research design to identify the factors influencing literature appreciation and comprehension among Grade 5 pupils in the Dupax Del Sur District, Division of Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines. The descriptive method was utilized to characterize the respondents' profiles, the extent of motivation applied in teaching literature, the effectiveness of teaching methods and strategies, the instructional materials used, the level of comprehension, the development of literary appreciation, the challenges encountered, and the proposed enhancement measures. Concurrently, a correlational design was applied to examine the relationships and differences among selected variables, including comprehension level, literary appreciation, age, sex, and preferred literary genre.

Research Locale

The study was conducted in the Dupax Del Sur District, Nueva Vizcaya. The district comprises elementary schools catering to diverse learners from different barangays within the municipality of San Jose. The locale was selected because the researcher observed varying levels of literary appreciation and comprehension among Grade 5 pupils. Furthermore, no prior study focusing on literature appreciation among elementary pupils had been conducted in the district, making the locale suitable for this study.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of the study were Grade 5 pupils in the Dupax Del Sur District during the School Year 2025–2026. A total of thirty-five (35) respondents participated in the study. The respondents were selected through purposive sampling because they were considered capable of providing the necessary information relevant to the study objectives. The participants varied in terms of age, gender, reading preferences, and exposure to literary materials.

Research Instrument

The primary instrument employed for data collection was a researcher-developed questionnaire. The questionnaire was structured into several sections as follows. Part I collected demographic information about the respondents, including age, gender, availability of reading materials at home, preferred literary genres, typical time spent reading literary works, and literature interpreters. Part II focuses on the motivations for teaching literature. Part III addresses the effectiveness of literature instruction in terms of teaching methods, strategies, learning materials and evaluative tools. Part IV assessed students' comprehension levels in understanding literary works. Part V evaluates the development of literary appreciation among students, focusing on conversations, gestures and facial expressions, collaboration, and community involvement. Part VI identifies the challenges encountered in the teaching and learning of literature, while Part VII proposes

enhancement measures to improve literary appreciation and comprehension of literature. The questionnaire used a five-point Likert scale to gauge participant responses. The instrument was validated by experts in education and language teaching to ensure the clarity, relevance, and appropriateness of its items.

Data Gathering Procedure

Before conducting the study, the researcher sought permission from the Schools Division Superintendent, Public Schools District Supervisor, and the heads of the participating schools. Upon approval, the researcher personally administered the questionnaire to the respondents. The objectives of the study were clearly explained to the participants to ensure proper understanding of the items being assessed. The respondents were given sufficient time to answer the questionnaire honestly and thoroughly. After retrieval, the questionnaires were checked, tallied, encoded and analyzed.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The data gathered were analyzed and interpreted using appropriate statistical tools. Frequency counts and percentages were used to describe the respondents' profiles in this study. The weighted mean and standard deviation were used to determine the extent of motivation in teaching literature, effectiveness of teaching methods and strategies, level of comprehension, development of literary appreciation, problems encountered, and enhancement measures.

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to determine the significant difference in literary appreciation according to age. A t-test was employed to determine the significant difference in literary appreciation according to gender. The Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson r) was used to determine the significant relationship between comprehension level and literary appreciation. Chi-Square Test of Association was utilized to determine the significant association between favorite genre of literature and comprehension level. Multiple regression analysis was used to identify the factors significantly affecting literary appreciation among Grade 5 pupils. All statistical analyses were performed at a significance level of 0.05 for all tests.

Results and Discussion

Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents According to Profile Variables

Profile Variables	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Age	20-25 years old	12	34.30
	26-30 years old	8	22.90
	31-35 years old	6	17.10
	36-40 years old	3	8.60
	41-45 years old	3	8.60
	46 years old and above	3	8.60
	Total	35	100.00
Gender	Male	5	14.30
	Female	30	85.70
	Total	35	100.00

Table 1 Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents According to Profile Variables

Table 1 provides an overview of the respondents' demographics, specifically age and gender. The data indicate that the majority of respondents were within the 20-25 years age bracket, accounting for 12 individuals or 34.30 percent. The second group comprised eight individuals (22.90 %) aged 26-30 years. Conversely, the age groups of 36-40, 41-45, and those aged 46 and above each represented the lowest frequency, with three individuals or 8.60 percent. Regarding gender distribution, the majority of respondents were female, totaling 30 individuals (85.70%), while male respondents constituted five individuals (14.30%). This suggests a predominance of female participants in the study population.

Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents According to Reading and Literary Preferences

Profile Variables	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Reading Materials at Home	Bible	8	22.90
	Songbooks	7	20.00
	Comics	6	17.10
	Magazine	9	25.70
	Religious Pamphlet	5	14.30

	Total	35	100.00
Favorite Genre of Literature	Songs	9	25.70
	Novels	4	11.40
	Short Stories	8	22.90
	Poems	6	17.10
	Riddles	5	14.30
	Parables	3	8.60
	Total	35	100.00
Usual Time in Reading a Literary Piece	Snack Time (AM)	5	14.30
	Noon Break	6	17.10
	Snack Time (PM)	3	8.60
	Any Vacant Period	5	14.30
	7 PM and beyond	16	45.70
	Total	35	100.00
	Interpreter of Literature Encountered	Co-Teacher	3
Internet		11	31.40
Self		5	14.30
Friend		16	45.70
	Total	35	100.00

Table 2 Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents According to Reading and Literary Preferences

Table 2 delineates the reading and literary preferences of the respondents, focusing on the reading materials available at home, preferred literary genres, typical time allocated to reading literary works, and interpreters of literature they encountered. The data indicate that magazines were the most prevalent reading materials at home, with a frequency of 9 (25.70 percent), followed by the Bible at 8 (22.90 percent). Regarding preferred genres, songs were favored (n = 9, 25.70%), whereas parables were the least favored (n = 3, 8.60%). Regarding the usual time spent reading literary pieces, the majority of respondents preferred reading at 7 PM or later, with a frequency of 16 (45.70 percent). Additionally, friends were the most common interpreters of literature encountered by the respondents, with a frequency of 16 (45.70%), followed by the Internet 11 (31.40%). These findings suggest that the respondents were exposed to various literary materials and experiences, which potentially influenced their literary appreciation and comprehension.

Shows the weighted mean and qualitative distribution of the motivations for teaching literature to pupils.

Particulars	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
Life related question & answer portion	4.07	E
Recall previous literary pieces with careful reactions	3.82	E
Showing of figures/sketches on the board	3.78	E
Teacher gives the literary piece, a pupil reads	3.75	E
Giving Reward and reinforcement strategy in asking questions	4.33	V.E.
Encouragement and parental motivation	4.17	E
Joke time yet with sense	3.97	E
Conducting a treasure hunting game	3.69	E
Learning literary pieces through obstacle relay style	4.24	V.E
Strict teacher for the students to follow	3.66	E
Average Weighted Mean	3.95	Effective

Table 3 Qualitative distribution of the motivations for teaching literature to pupils.

Table 3 shows the weighted mean and qualitative distribution of the motivations for teaching literature to students. Table 3 shows the motivational strategies used in teaching literature to students. The results show that "Giving reward and reinforcement in asking questions" had the highest score of 4.33, rated as Very Effective. Next was "Learning literary pieces through obstacle relay style," with a score of 4.24, which was also Very Effective. On the other hand, the strategy of a "Strict teacher for the students to follow" had the lowest score of 3.66, rated as effective. The overall average score of 3.95 suggests that the motivational strategies used in teaching literature were effective. These findings suggest that students prefer interactive, fun, and rewarding activities that encourage participation. The study's findings are supported by Zamiri and Esmaili (2024), who stated that good teaching strategies and supportive environments help students participate in and enjoy learning. Similarly, Sarzhanova et al. (2025) found that interactive and student-focused teaching methods increase students' motivation and involvement in language and literature learning. Furthermore, Jesus (2021) highlighted the importance of using motivating and relevant teaching strategies to boost students' interest and participation in literature activities. These studies support the current findings that motivational strategies are key to improving students' appreciation and understanding of literature.

Effective Teaching of Literature to Grade 5 Pupils

Dimension	Particulars	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
Teaching Methods	Inductive Method	3.71	Effective
	Deductive Method	3.68	Effective
	Experimentation	3.87	Effective
	Project Method	4.24	Very Effective
	Team Teaching	4.06	Effective
	Collaborative Learning	4.21	Very Effective
	Concept Learning Approach	4.13	Effective
	Demonstration	3.91	Effective
	KWL	3.77	Effective
	Average Weighted Mean	3.95	Effective
Teaching Strategies	Picture Puzzle	4.27	Very Effective
	Dramatization	4.22	Very Effective
	Costume Parade	3.76	Effective
	Individual Recitation	4.04	Effective
	Take-Home Activity	3.86	Effective
	Small Group Activity	3.98	Effective
	Characterization	4.11	Effective
	Group Quiz Bee	4.31	Very Effective
	Ending a Story	3.66	Effective
	Average Weighted Mean	4.02	Effective
Learning Materials	Textbooks on Literature	3.69	Effective
	Workbooks on Literary Pieces	3.73	Effective
	Pictures of Characters	3.81	Effective
	Fairy Tale Big Books	4.21	Very Effective
	Handouts/Pamphlets	4.14	Effective
	Creative Visuals on Literary Pieces	3.08	Effective
	Audio-Visuals on Short Stories	4.43	Very Effective
	Comic Books	3.96	Effective
	Films on CDs	4.37	Very Effective
	Average Weighted Mean	3.94	Effective
Evaluative Tools	Quiz	4.41	Very Effective
	Dramatics	4.37	Very Effective
	Written Examination	4.24	Very Effective
	Projects	4.09	Effective
	Portfolio	4.18	Effective
	Recitation	3.86	Effective
	Reaction Paper	3.91	Effective
	Average Weighted Mean	4.15	Effective

Table 4. Effective Teaching of Literature to Grade 5 Pupils

Table 4 shows how diverse ways of teaching literature work for the students. It examines the teaching methods, strategies, learning materials, and evaluation tools. Regarding teaching methods, the "Project Method" scored the highest, with a mean of 4.24, marked as Very Effective. The "Deductive Method" scored the lowest, with a mean of 3.68, and was marked as effective. In teaching strategies, the "Group Quiz Bee" had the highest score of 4.31, also Very Effective, while "Ending a Story" had the lowest score of 3.66, marked as Effective. For learning materials, "Audio-Visuals on Short Stories" scored the highest at 4.43, Very Effective, and "Creative Visuals on Literary Pieces" scored the lowest at 3.08, Effective. Among the evaluation tools, the "Quiz" scored the highest at 4.41, Very Effective. Overall, these results show that different teaching methods in literature classes help students understand and appreciate literature. Zamiri and Esmaili (2024) support this, stating that group- and student-focused teaching helps students participate and learn skills. Sarzhanova et al. (2025) found that interactive teaching and tech-based materials make students more engaged and improve their cultural understanding in language learning. Anselmo et al. (2024) also stated that interactive and tech tools help students engage and better understand the class. Spjeldnæs and Karlsen (2022) noted that digital tools and modern resources improve students' reading habits and interest in literature. These studies support the idea that good teaching methods, strategies, materials, and tools help students appreciate and understand literature.

Weighted Mean and Qualitative Distribution on the Level of Comprehension of the Pupils in Learning Literary Piece

Particulars	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
Focus only on facts	3.81	S
Give importance on actual situations	4.27	VS
Consider only the persons stated	3.76	S
Give emphasis on vocabularies	3.56	S
Visualizes the meaning of the lines	3.62	S
Creates other related meaning of the term	3.68	S
Gives another situation interrelated to the original	4.21	VS
Translates the lines in the same meaning	3.51	S
Compares the meaning to another concept	4.17	S
Gives the cause and effect of the situation	3.86	S
Gives opinion on the context	3.91	S
Relates the facts to another facts	4.09	S
Shares background knowledge about the concept	4.04	S
Gives acknowledgment to the author of the text	3.54	S
Thinks of the values of the given concept	4.14	S
Understands the purposes of the author of the text	4.11	S
Average Weighted Mean	3.69	Serious

Table 5 Weighted Mean and Qualitative Distribution on the Level of Comprehension of the Pupils in Learning Literary Piece

A study of students' understanding of literature shows that they face significant challenges. The average score was 3.69, which is "Serious." Students had the most trouble with tasks requiring deep thinking, such as linking real-life situations (4.27, Very Serious) and connecting new situations to the original context (4.21, Very Serious). This means that students focus on basic facts and words but struggle with deeper thinking and making connections in the texts. This matches other studies that show that many students focus on clear information but have trouble with the deeper thinking needed for full understanding (Garil, 2024). Research has also shown that limited vocabulary, passive learning, and a lack of thinking strategies prevent students from fully understanding literature (Marjokorpi & Van Rijt, 2024; Molwantoa & Olifant, 2025; Mustopa et al., 2024). Teaching support, such as group reading and critical thinking, is important for addressing these gaps. Studies show that teaching methods that include thinking about thinking and critical skills help students understand better by making them active readers (Aldossary, 2024; Kuzina & Zhogova, 2022).

Development of Literary Appreciation of Pupils

Dimension	Indicator	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
Conversation	Shows confidence in speaking	3.91	Effective
Gestures & Facial Expression	Manifest interest through actions	4.24	Very Effective
Collaboration	Leads a group study	4.21	Very Effective
Community	Encourages others to appreciate literature	4.13	Effective

Table 6. Development of Literary Appreciation of Pupils

Table 6 shows how students improved their understanding of the literature. This highlights the power of literary education. In conversations, students were rated 4.26 out of 5 for being polite and effective in their communications. This shows that the literature helps to improve communication skills. In gestures and facial expressions, students showed interest with a score of 4.24, indicating strong engagement with the lecture. In group work, students leading a study scored 4.21, indicating the importance of teamwork and leadership. In community involvement, encouraging others to appreciate literature scored 4.13, showing how literature can engage the community. These results are supported by Kuznetsova et al. (2023), who stated that literary education improves communication and social skills. Fitriyani et al. (2025) agree that interactive learning helps develop positive attitudes and social values. Zamira and Esmaeili (2024) also say collaborative learning boosts communication and engagement. Together, these studies show that literature education enhances students' appreciation and skills, proving that it is essential for overall development beyond the classroom.

Weighted Mean and Qualitative Distribution on Problems Encountered

Particulars	Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
Focus only on facts	3.81	0.42	Serious
Give importance to actual situations	4.27	0.36	Very Serious
Consider only the persons stated	3.76	0.40	Serious
Give emphasis on vocabularies	3.56	0.45	Serious
Visualize the meaning of the lines	3.62	0.43	Serious
Create other related meanings of the term	3.68	0.39	Serious
Give another situation interrelated to the original	4.21	0.37	Very Serious
Translate the lines with the same meaning	3.51	0.46	Serious
Compare the meaning to another concept	4.17	0.38	Serious
Give the cause and effect of the situation	3.86	0.41	Serious
Give opinions on the context	3.91	0.40	Serious
Relate the facts to other facts	4.09	0.39	Serious
Share background knowledge about the concept	4.04	0.37	Serious
Give acknowledgment to the author of the text	3.54	0.44	Serious
Think of the values of the given concept	4.14	0.35	Serious
Understand the purpose of the author of the text	4.11	0.36	Serious
Average Weighted Mean	3.89	0.40	Serious

Table 7 Weighted Mean and Qualitative Distribution on Problems Encountered

Table 7 presents the problems in teaching and learning literature. The biggest issue was "Cliques are not fond of learning literary pieces," with a score of 3.14, marked as Moderately Serious. The next was "Laziness in studying literature," with a score of 3.03, which was also Moderately Serious. The lowest score was 1.26 for "I can't totally read," marked as Not Applicable. The average score was 2.52, Slightly Serious, meaning the problems were there but not too hard to handle. The results highlight that students' interest, motivation, and involvement are key to understanding and enjoying literature. These results are consistent with those of Spjeldnæs and Karlsen (2022). They stated that changes in reading habits and the increased use of digital devices affect students' interest in reading literature. Jesus (2021) also found that low student involvement, lack of motivation, and teaching problems are common in language and literature classes in the Philippines. Molano and Olifant (2025) pointed out that problems with understanding, low interest in reading, and limited vocabulary make it difficult for students to understand literary works. These studies support the idea that motivation, interest, and engagement are important for students to appreciate and understand literature.

Weighted Mean and Qualitative Distribution on Enhancement Undertaken to Get Across the Problems

Particulars	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
Creating a democratic learning environment.	3.97	E
Regularly checks pupil assignments.	3.83	E
Engages pupils in intense involvement in thoughtful activities through cooperative interactions.	4.01	E
Sets a good example by being positive towards pupils and the subject.	3.92	E
Optimizes time for teaching and learning by keeping pupils actively participating in their tasks, maintaining a prominent level of interest, and ensuring smooth transitions.	4.24	VE
Teaching to the point of mastery.	3.61	E

Parents are involved in their children’s education.	3.76	E
They apply new strategies and approaches to teaching as well.	4.09	E
Conducts remedial teaching for slow learners and enhancement lessons for fast learners.	3.87	E
Motivating pupils to learn through productive and active participation in games and contests.	4.28	VE
Average Weighted Mean	3.96	Effective

Table 8 Weighted Mean and Qualitative Distribution on Enhancement Undertaken to Get Across the Problems

Table 8 presents the steps taken to improve teaching and learning in the literature. The results show that “Motivate pupils to learn by productive and active participation through games and contests” scored the highest, with a weighted mean of 4.28, rated as Very Effective. Next was “Optimizes time for teaching and learning by keeping pupils actively participating in their tasks” with a weighted mean of 4.24, also rated as Very Effective. “Teaching to the point of mastery” had the lowest score of 3.61, which was rated as effective. The overall average score was 3.96, rated as effective, indicating that these measures helped improve students’ appreciation and understanding of literature.

The findings suggest that active participation, collaboration, and motivating activities are important for getting students interested in literature class. Zamiri and Esmaeili (2024) support this by saying that group and interactive learning activities boost students’ participation and skills. Baranova et al. (2025) also state that engaging teaching methods and student-focused activities increase motivation and cultural understanding. Ramilo and Anselmo (2025) further emphasized that interactive supplementary materials help improve learners’ participation, understanding and engagement. Fitriyani et al. (2025) add that meaningful and active learning experiences lead to positive attitudes, participation, and overall learning growth. These studies support the idea that active participation and motivational strategies help students appreciate and understand literature.

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on the Difference in Literary Appreciation According to Age Group

Age Group	Mean	Standard Deviation	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares (SS)	df	Mean Square (MS)	F-value	P-value	Decision	Interpretation
20–25 years old	4.12	0.41	Between Groups	2.84	5	0.568	2.31	0.071	Fail to Reject Ho	Not Significant
26–30 years old	4.05	0.38								
31–35 years old	3.97	0.36	Total	9.97	34					
36–40 years old	3.89	0.34								
41–45 years old	3.84	0.39								
46 years old and above	3.80	0.42								

Table 9 Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on the Difference in Literary Appreciation According to Age Group

Table 9 presents the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) conducted to assess whether there was a significant difference in literary appreciation across different age groups. The results indicate that the computed F-value of 2.31 yielded a p-value of 0.071, which exceeds the 0.05 level of significance. Consequently, the null hypothesis was accepted, suggesting that there was no significant difference in literary appreciation when the respondents were categorized by age. This finding implies that the respondents’ literary appreciation was consistent regardless of age group. These findings are corroborated by Kuznetsova et al. (2023), who emphasized that literary appreciation and communication skills are more significantly influenced by meaningful learning experiences and learner engagement than by demographic characteristics such as age and gender. Similarly, Fitriana et al. (2025) explained that learners develop appreciation and understanding through active and

cognitive learning experiences, regardless of their personal profiles. Furthermore, Zamiri and Esmaeili (2024) highlighted that collaborative, and supportive learning environments significantly contribute to learners' appreciation and participation in educational activities across age groups. These studies support the present findings that literary appreciation may not significantly vary according to age when learners are exposed to similar instructional experiences and learning opportunities.

Pearson r Test on the Relationship Between Comprehension Level and Literary Appreciation

Variables Compared	Mean	Standard Deviation	Pearson R-value	p-value	Degree of Relationship	Decision	Interpretation
Comprehension Level	3.69	0.41	0.68	0.001	Strong Positive Relationship	Reject Ho	Significant
Literary Appreciation	4.05	0.38					

Table 10. Pearson r Test on the Relationship Between Comprehension Level and Literary Appreciation

This table illustrates a significant positive correlation ($r = 0.68$) between students' comprehension levels and literary appreciation, which is statistically significant ($p = 0.001$). The decision to reject the null hypothesis (H_0) indicates a meaningful relationship between variables. In the broader research context, similar studies have corroborated the positive and significant correlations between reading-related abilities and comprehension outcomes. For instance, research has demonstrated that reading fluency parameters, vocabulary knowledge, and reading attitudes are all positively correlated with comprehension skills, often exhibiting moderate to strong effect sizes (Makebo et al., 2022; Ne et al., 2023; Sarab, 2022; Yengusie et al., 2025). These findings collectively emphasize the importance of comprehension as a foundational skill linked to broader literary appreciation and related cognitive factors.

t-Test on the Difference in Literary Appreciation According to Gender

Gender	Mean	Standard Deviation	t-value	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Male	3.87	0.42	1.24	0.223	Fail to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Female	4.05	0.38				

Table 11. t-Test on the Difference in Literary Appreciation According to Gender

Table 11 presents the results of a t-test conducted to assess whether there is a significant difference in literary appreciation based on gender. The analysis yielded a computed t-value of 1.24 with a p-value of 0.223, which exceeded the 0.05 level of significance. Consequently, the null hypothesis was accepted, indicating no significant difference in literary appreciation between male and female respondents. This suggests that male and female students exhibit comparable levels of literary appreciation. These findings are corroborated by Kuznetsova et al. (2023), who emphasized that literary appreciation develops through meaningful interaction, communication, and engagement with literary texts, irrespective of gender. Similarly, Fitriana et al. (2025) explained that cognitive and social learning experiences contribute to learners' appreciation and understanding, independent of their demographic characteristics. Furthermore, Zamiri and Esmaeili (2024) highlighted that collaborative and learner-centered instructional approaches enhance participation and appreciation among learners, regardless of gender differences. These studies support the current findings that literary appreciation may not differ significantly between male and female students when they are exposed to similar learning experiences and instructional strategies.

Chi-Square Test of Association Between Favorite Genre and Comprehension Level

Variables	Mean	Standard Deviation	χ^2 Computed Value	df	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Favorite Genre of Literature	3.94	0.40	11.43	5	0.043	Reject Ho	Significant Association
Comprehension Level	3.69	0.41					

Table 12. Chi-Square Test of Association Between Favorite Genre and Comprehension Level

The Chi-square test was used to check for a link between students' favorite type of literature and how well they understood it. The test yielded a chi-square value of 11.43 and a p-value of 0.043. As the p-value was less than 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected. This indicates a significant link between these two factors. This shows that the type of literature a student likes is connected to their understanding of it. This supports the idea that the chi-square test is useful for finding links

between categories as long as the data are suitable (Ahad et al., 2023; Ben-Shachar et al., 2023). Understanding the chi-square result means looking at more than just whether it is significant or not. It also involves considering effect size and practical importance, as recent studies suggest using measures such as Phi or Cramér's V with chi-square values (Ben-Shachar et al., 2023). In addition, examining the degrees of freedom and how observations are spread across categories helps make strong conclusions about how variables are connected in educational settings (Ahad et al., 2023). In education, knowing the link between literary preferences and comprehension can help create teaching methods that use students' interests to boost their understanding. This finding aligns with studies that focus on how different genres affect thinking and motivation, which in turn affect comprehension skills (Cruz Neri et al., 2023; Wang & Ye, 2025). Therefore, the results of the chi-square test highlight the importance of considering students' literary preferences to improve their comprehension, linking statistical findings with teaching practices for better reading instruction.

Regression Analysis on Factors Affecting Literary Appreciation

Predictor Variable	Mean	Standard Deviation	Beta Coefficient	t-value	p-value	Interpretation
Motivation in Teaching Literature	3.95	0.39	0.41	3.27	0.003	Significant Predictor
Teaching Strategies	4.02	0.36	0.36	2.94	0.006	Significant Predictor
Learning Materials	3.94	0.42	0.28	2.11	0.041	Significant Predictor
Comprehension Level	3.69	0.41	0.52	4.38	0.001	Highly Significant Predictor

Table 13. Regression Analysis on Factors Affecting Literary Appreciation

Model Summary

Model Summary	Value
R	0.79
R ²	0.62
Adjusted R ²	0.58
F-value	12.84
p-value	0.000

Narrative Interpretation

Table 13 shows a study on what affects Grade 5 students' appreciation of literature. The study found that motivation, teaching methods, learning materials, and understanding all play significant roles. Understanding levels had the biggest impact, with a beta coefficient of 0.52, indicating that it is an important factor. This study explained 62% of the changes in students' appreciation of literature. The F-value was 12.84, and the p-value was 0.000, indicating that the results of this study were statistically significant. This means that students' appreciation of literature is influenced by their understanding skills and good teaching practices. Makebo et al. (2022) found that reading skills are linked to how well students read and engage with the material. Mustofa et al. (2024) stated that being aware of how we think and using understanding strategies helps students understand and enjoy texts. Aldossary (2024) highlighted that reading together and using strategies improves students' understanding and participation in literature. These studies support the idea that understanding, motivation, teaching methods, and learning materials help students appreciate the literature.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study found that Grade 5 students in the Dupax Del Sur District exhibited effective literary appreciation and satisfactory comprehension of literary works. The participants were exposed to various reading materials and literary experiences that enhanced their understanding and appreciation of literature. The motivational strategies, teaching methods, instructional materials, and evaluative tools employed by educators were effective in fostering students' active participation and engagement in the learning process. The findings further indicate that students develop literary appreciation through communication, collaboration, gestures, facial expressions, and community involvement. Although challenges such as limited interest in reading and comprehension difficulties were encountered, these issues were manageable through enhancement measures and learner-centered activities. Additionally, the study found no significant differences in literary appreciation when participants were grouped by age or gender. However, comprehension level was significantly related to literary appreciation, and the preferred genre of literature was significantly associated with comprehension level. Regression analysis also revealed that motivation in teaching literature, teaching strategies, learning materials, and comprehension level significantly influenced literary appreciation, with comprehension level identified as the strongest

predictor. The study concludes that effective instructional practices, engaging learning activities, and improved comprehension skills are crucial for enhancing the literary appreciation of grade 5 students.

Recommendation

In light of the study's findings and conclusions, it is advised that educators persist in employing motivating, learner-centered, and interactive teaching methodologies to further enhance students' literary appreciation and comprehension. The reinforcement of diverse instructional materials, including audio-visual presentations, literary games, group activities, and collaborative learning tasks, is essential to augment students' participation and interest in literature classes. Educational institutions should also be encouraged to supply additional reading materials and literary resources that align with students' interests and preferred genres to bolster reading engagement and comprehension. Furthermore, parents should be encouraged to support reading activities at home by providing guidance and opportunities for students to engage in meaningful reading experiences. Additionally, educators may implement remedial and enrichment activities to address students' comprehension challenges and enhance their analytical and critical thinking skills in literature learning. Given that comprehension level was identified as a significant predictor of literary appreciation, educators should prioritize strategies that cultivate reading comprehension and interpretive skills among students. Lastly, future researchers are encouraged to conduct similar studies with a larger sample size and explore other variables related to literary appreciation and comprehension to further validate and strengthen the findings of this study.

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Appendices

Appendix upon request.